

ISSUES OF TEACHING AZERBAIJAN MORPHOLOGY

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Fresh Currently, national education in Azerbaijan is in a stage of development that is in line with human values and gives importance to these values. The rise of our language to such a stage requires great attention and responsibility from scientists and educators. There are a number of problems in curricula and textbooks that cause concern. It is the duty and responsibility of each of us to be very careful in modern science and education. Problems in the fields of science should also be approached from this perspective, and shortcomings in this aspect should be eliminated. The article highlights the problems related to the teaching of the morphology of the Azerbaijani language.

Keywords: science, language, teaching, problem, method.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching sciences justifies their deeper and more detailed study. From this point of view, teaching the Azerbaijani language is an interesting and relevant process. In teaching the Azerbaijani language, practical language materials should be followed more closely, and their problematic aspects should be revealed. In this sense, the issues of teaching morphology attract attention. Although the concepts of parts of speech, and morphological concepts in general, have been studied and analyzed to some extent in Azerbaijani linguistics, it is necessary to conduct a number of studies related to that area of grammar. Thus, researchers who deal with grammar have mainly focused on theoretical issues. However, problematic issues arise more often during teaching. In this sense, teaching the morphology of the Azerbaijani language is one of the interesting and relevant topics.

METHOD. The study used the linguistic analysis method to analyze some morphological facts in the study of the modern Azerbaijani language, the descriptive method to present linguistic facts, and the comparative method to analyze theoretical ideas on the topic.

DISCUSSION

Teaching grammar is one of the important, interesting and necessary issues of the pedagogical process. Since, on the one hand, it ensures the high development of grammatical thinking skills, on the other hand, it allows our speech to adapt to the norms of the literary language and strengthen these norms. "A person who is unable to correctly case a word and correctly change the verb according to tense, undoubtedly cannot acquire normal language habits, since he cannot even observe ordinary grammatical norms in his speech" (Baliyev (2003), p. 275).

A number of problems are revealed in the grammar of the Azerbaijani language, which should be clarified in the teaching process. There are some issues that need to be identified in the teaching of morphological topics, which should be given special attention in the pedagogical process. It is known that the alphabet of parts of speech begins with a noun. Therefore, initially,

the solution of problematic issues should begin with its teaching. "...If nouns, or rather, objective beings, phenomena, ideas about being, and the imaginary concepts they express, did not exist, there would be no qualities, signs, quantities and actions inherent in them. Therefore, the teaching of nouns takes the first place in teaching parts of speech, and in grammar lessons, the teaching of parts of speech begins with a noun" (Jafarov (1962), p. 6).

One of the points that causes confusion in the teaching of nouns is related to their case category. A number of ideas have been put forward regarding the case category in our historical and contemporary grammar. Finally, it was accepted that there are six cases in nouns, and it was shown that two of them have two forms (definite and indefinite).

It is known that a large group of words in the language - except for verbs, the remaining main parts of speech adopt the morphological features of a number of categories (case, belonging, quantity, information), that is, become nouns. In this sense, one of the main parts of speech that attracts attention is the adverb. It is known that not all adverbs, for example, adverbs of quantity and manner, are cased. However, adverbs of time and place are cased. For example:

Don't put off today's work until tomorrow.

Strange sounds are coming from below.

There is darkness ahead, etc.

When adverbs of time accept the case markers of the noun, the feature of uncertainty also manifests itself in the case of direction:

Fidan entered, etc.

The above-mentioned facts show that the noun has not only possessive and active cases, but also two types of direction cases (definite and indefinite). During the teaching of morphology in higher education institutions, drawing students' attention to the aforementioned issues contributes to the development of science, increases interest in it, and also provides students with relevant, original, and research-worthy topics for their scientific work.

Experience shows that one of the issues that creates confusion in the teaching process is the failure to distinguish between nouns denoting place and adverbs of place. As a result, nouns are sometimes attributed to adverbs of place. "In academic grammar, there are more unscientific facts about nouns that are attributed to adverbs of place, and all this seriously harms the teaching process" (Aliyev(2006), p.19).

It is even more regrettable that ideas that do not fit into scientific logic are put forward about adverbs. For example, how can one accept the idea that adverbs denoting place are considered nouns: "Words such as forward, backward, right, left, down, and outside are nouns denoting direction that are not reflected in grammar books" (Aliyev (2006), p. 19). This raises the following question: If the language units in question are nouns, what are adverbs of place? Maybe there is no adverb of place at all in our language? In our opinion, the reason for this confusion is the inability to distinguish between nouns denoting place and adverbs.

In some scientific literature, we come across facts of mixing nouns and adverbs (Huseynzadeh (2004), p. 145). They claim that an adverb becomes a noun when it accepts the case of the noun. However, these ideas cannot be justified. If we approach them from a logical point of view, these considerations have no scientific basis. Regardless of whether the noun accepts the morphological sign of the case category or not, adverbs of place are always adverbs and they should be taught as adverbs. That is, they carry the concept of an adverb both when accepting the directional suffix and without that case suffix.

Thus, it is worth talking about the case of indefinite directionality. We cannot ignore the ambiguity that manifests itself both in the adverb of place and in the interrogative pronoun "where?". Because in language, not only facts related to several parts of speech, but even signs are of great importance and meaning. From this point of view, every fact in the language has its essence and is worthy of scientific and theoretical ideas.

Studies show that the adverb has been in the center of attention of scientific and theoretical thought at different times (and now) as one of the linguistic units that causes controversial points among the main parts of speech. Especially when it comes to adverbial suffixes, it has caused more controversy: "Although the suffixes in adverbs resemble case suffixes, it is not correct to consider them as true case suffixes. They must be suffixes of a different nature" (Jafarov S. (1962), p. 33). It is difficult to agree with this opinion. Because a number of adverbs can be cased, and this is one of the natural processes in the language. However, one thing we can agree on regarding the suffix -da is that it is not always used as a case suffix, but also serves to form adverbs.

By the way, we should note that currently the concept of uncertainty in the Azerbaijani language has expanded significantly and can now be spoken of as a category. This issue, which manifests itself in grammar – both in morphology (indefinite possessive case, indefinite active case, indefinite directional case, indefinite quantifiers, indefinite pronouns) and syntax (indefinite person sentences, etc.), has already become a category.

There are also problems that attract attention in the teaching of adjectives. One of them is the degrees of the adjective. In linguistic literature, the degree sign is noted as the main feature that distinguishes adjectives from other parts of speech, and its relevance is shown only in relation to adjectives. However, modern linguistic facts show that the morphological features of the degree are also used in other parts of speech. Therefore, the concept of degree cannot be limited to adjectives alone, its scope is wider, and there is a need to accept the degree as a category and include it in the list of grammatical categories, which is also confirmed by the facts in the language.

One of the morphological features that form adjectives is the suffix $-k_1^4$, which is written in four ways. According to scientific literature, this suffix creates adjectives from adverbs of time. However, the parts of speech to which this suffix is attached cannot be limited to adverbs.

Unfortunately, in some scientific-methodological literature there are also unscientific opinions about the suffix in question. Thus, it is also attached to adjectives and demonstrative pronouns. Thus, it is claimed that this suffix has three variants (Aliyev (2006), p. 39). The suffix -ki does not have three variants (there are no three-variant, i.e. three-way suffixes in the Azerbaijani language, suffixes are divided into three types according to their spelling:

1. Suffixes written in one way.
2. Suffixes written in two ways.
3. Suffixes written in four ways).

It is known that suffixes express different meanings (name, attribute) from a semantic point of view. It both expresses possession and belonging by joining nouns and pronouns, and it also creates adjectives by joining various parts of speech, mainly adverbs of time, and in both cases it is written in four ways.

In addition, we encounter a number of other unscientific ideas, which, if we rely on them, will not lead to the correct result in the teaching process. For example, such an idea attracts attention that "...it is illogical to claim that a case suffix is attached to a word twice" (Aliyev (2006), p. 39). However, although this "does not fit into logic", it is consistent with linguistic facts. We must not forget that there are exceptions in language and that every fact is important. Let us not forget that "...a linguistic fact is more reliable than any historical document" (Guliyeva, Hajiyevev (2006), p. 160). Yes, a noun can be in one case and a verb in the same tense. However, linguistic facts show that two case suffixes can be used in one word. This happens when a lexical suffix is necessarily present between two case suffixes. That is, two case suffixes cannot be used together, they can be used in separate places in the word. For example:

I bought my book, I forgot to buy yours.

Here, the word yours has two case suffixes:

1. Possessive case (-in).
2. Active case (-i).

If these are not case category suffixes, then what are they? If a case suffix is followed by a lexical suffix, this does not mean that they should be taken in the same

composition. Therefore, a grammatical sign and a lexical sign should not be considered the same suffix.

By the way, when teaching case suffixes, and suffixes in general, it is necessary to pay attention to whether they are stressed or not (Stress is one of the difficult topics in linguistics, and its teaching cannot be limited to phonetics alone). It is known that in all literature on stress, ideas have been formed and have already been fixed that case suffixes of nouns accept stress. However, there are also points where case suffixes do not accept stress. For example, if the case suffix is preceded by a lexical suffix -gil, which is written in a certain way, then the case suffix cannot accept stress. Because the suffix -gil itself does not accept stress, and does not leave the stress to the suffixes that follow it. As you can see, there are many confusing issues in the language (which even confuse experts), and when discussing them in the teaching process, one should be based on facts and try to draw the correct conclusion from these facts.

Teaching numbers is also an interesting pedagogical process. Linguistic literature shows that numbers do not participate in word formation, in fact, they participate, but are not active. Numbers are not formed from other parts of speech, they are formed by themselves. However, a number of parts of speech are formed from numbers (for example, nouns (union), adjectives (thirty), verbs (to unite), etc.). It is known that ordinal numbers are formed with the suffix -inci, -inci, -unci, -unci. This suffix is also added to the interrogative pronoun "how many?"

The Azerbaijani language plays an important role in all public events of the independent Republic of Azerbaijan. Using this language, it is possible to make speeches from high podiums and exchange ideas with listeners. Currently, the state pays great attention to the development of the Azerbaijani language in our country, and many official documents are signed in this area. "The first decade of the 21st century is characterized as a period of radical changes in the Azerbaijani education system. It can be said without exaggeration that a new era begins in this process for teaching the native language" (Nabiyeva (2010), p. 7). The Azerbaijani language has a communicative purpose. From this point of view, its teaching should always be kept in mind.

By the way, when teaching case suffixes, and suffixes in general, it is necessary to pay attention to their stress (Stress is one of the difficult topics in linguistics, and its teaching cannot be limited to phonetics alone). It is known that in all literature on stress, ideas have been formed and have already been established that case suffixes of nouns accept stress. However, there are also points where case suffixes do not accept stress. For example, if the case suffix is preceded by a lexical suffix -gil, written in a certain order, the case suffix cannot accept stress. Because the suffix -gil itself does not accept stress, it does not leave the stress to the suffixes that follow it. As you can see, there are many issues in the language that cause confusion (even confuse experts), and when discussing them in the teaching process, it is necessary to try to draw the correct conclusions from these facts, based on facts.

Teaching numbers is also an interesting pedagogical process. Linguistic literature shows that numbers do not participate in word formation, in fact, they participate, but are not active. Numbers are mainly formed from the numbers themselves, not from other parts of speech. However, a number of parts of speech (some nouns, adjectives and verbs) are formed from numbers. It is known that ordinal numbers are formed with the suffixes -inchi, -inchi, -unci, -unci. This suffix is also added to the interrogative pronoun "neçe?" and forms a new word. It is necessary to touch upon such subtle issues during teaching.

The pronoun has a unique role and position as a controversial, comprehensive lexical-grammatical unit among the main parts of speech. The lack of a specific object has formed hesitant ideas about the pronoun in linguistics. The expressions "empty word", "mysterious word" have arisen regarding the pronoun, and in some cases it has been considered an auxiliary part of speech. Interestingly, confused ideas about the pronoun still persist, and scientific and theoretical ideas on the subject in linguistic literature do not coincide. In modern grammar books, especially in secondary school textbooks, it is possible to find a large number of confusing considerations on the subject of the pronoun. This also affects the teaching process.

The pronoun is a part of speech with great functions in the language and has many syntactic tasks. Its responsible and careful teaching helps to solve a number of morphological and syntactic issues. Since the pronoun replaces all the main parts of speech, its teaching allows for the expansion and deepening of knowledge about various parts of speech. "The pronouns of the Azerbaijani language can play a certain role in clarifying many issues in linguistics" (Nabiyeva (2010), p. 121). Since the pronoun can be used in place of all members of the sentence, its syntactic significance is also great. In modern linguistic literature, the pronoun is also evaluated as a factor that forms the text. "The pronoun, which becomes actual from independent parts of speech, plays an important role in the creation of relevant texts" (Abdullayev (1998), p. 129).

When teaching pronouns, attention should be paid primarily to the following issues:

1. The multiple functions of pronouns;
2. The lack of a specific subject compared to other main parts of speech;
3. The fact that pronouns are functional grammatical units in our language;
4. The fact that the pronoun answers the question of the part of speech in which it is used, etc.

The facts obtained as a result of experience show that pronouns are more conservative compared to other main parts of speech and have their own unique characteristics. One of the Azerbaijani grammarians, H. Mirzazadeh, also confirms this idea: "The pronouns existing in the Azerbaijani language have not undergone any serious changes during their development, and have remained stable in terms of meaning and function" (Abdullayev (1998), p. 104). Indeed, when comparing both historical and contemporary linguistic facts, it becomes clear that the changes related to pronouns have occurred in a formal (external) sense, and they have not

been subject to changes in terms of content (internal). Formal changes are phonetic changes. Considering the importance of a masculine sign in a language, it is necessary to take phonetic facts seriously during teaching. In this sense, it is also necessary to pay attention to its sound structure when teaching pronouns. Thus, the sound structure of pronouns used in our language, on the one hand, serves to determine the phonetic aspects reflecting the development of the period to which they belong, and on the other hand, it helps to teach grammatical units perfectly. From this we can conclude that treating the sound aspect of any morphological unit as a mere external form during teaching prevents its correct teaching as a whole.

In teaching grammar, the issue of the pronoun playing a very important role in speech should not be forgotten. Because in the speech process, the meaning of the pronoun in texts on various topics significantly affects the coherence of sentences and texts: "The meaning of the pronoun is often revealed by the content of the sentence preceding it. The fact that one of the sentences in the text begins with a pronoun is a fact that proves that it is more closely related to the sentences preceding it" (Abdullayev (1998), p. 132).

In teaching pronouns as a morphological unit, it is necessary to pay special attention to the fact that they are not subject to external interference and retain their nationality. The description and internal features of the pronoun, which is an ancient and national part of speech, are facts that show the strength of the genetic connection of Turkic languages. The pronoun is a language unit that has an important position in Turkic languages, including the Azerbaijani language, with its semantic, grammatical, and stylistic features. In this regard, there are wide opportunities for its high-quality teaching. Teaching pronouns in connection with specific language facts leads to useful results. On the one hand, this ensures the comprehensive mastery of the pronoun, and on the other hand, it justifies the formation of connections with other parts of speech.

Various methods can be used in teaching personal pronouns. Special attention should be paid to the first person pronouns (me, we) in the singular and plural. The difference that arises when these pronouns are used with case suffixes of nouns can be evaluated as one of their special features.

Teaching grammar is such an interesting and responsible process that the information provided on any issue must be confirmed by factual materials. Only then can we talk about the quality of teaching. If an opinion has ever been expressed or written about any linguistic fact, it would not be right to accept it as a standard. The most correct and accurate opinion about the language is the facts. In this regard, it is possible to find the necessary amount of material in the "Azerbaijani language" textbooks.

One of the issues that attracts attention in teaching pronouns is the consideration of local and dialectal features. Thus, depending on the regions, sometimes the pronouns "elə", "belə" are pronounced as "bəyla", "öylə" and this also affects the writing process. Since demonstrative pronouns are very functional lexical-

grammatical units for our grammar, special attention should be paid to them in the teaching process.

The Azerbaijani language has already entered a new stage of development, gaining unique qualities and enriching itself in terms of literary language norms. It is known that, in accordance with the development characteristics of society, processes of enrichment and change also occur in the language. In the Middle Ages, a number of common Turkic words entered the lexical-grammatical norms of our language, strengthened and gained an active position, and over time, these words became "Azerbaijanized" in terms of phonetics. However, at the beginning of the 20th century, in connection with the spread of Turkic ideas, the idea of a "common Turkic language" was formed, and the Azerbaijani language was based on the norms of the Turkish language for a while. Demonstrative pronouns are one of the lexical-grammatical examples that confirm this fact among the main parts of speech - the fact that the morphological norms of the Azerbaijani language gave way to the norms of the Turkish language. That is, although some pronouns were subject to archaism until that period, they were reactivated at the beginning of the 20th century and were selected for their frequency of use in our literary language for a while. This idea can be said about the pronouns "öylə", "böylə". Although these pronouns remained as a fact of speech after the second half of the 20th century, they have become completely archaic for the literary language. However, this obsolescence is not limited to the phonetic norm. The pronouns "öylə", "böylə" have given way to the pronouns "elə", "belə" with the same content and have disappeared from our writing. These pronouns remain as a fact of the norm in modern Turkish, while *biism* lives in our language only as an example of dialect and accent. Therefore, it is necessary to approach this issue sensitively in the teaching of grammar, especially pronouns.

The issues related to interrogative pronouns, which are one of the linguistic facts that attract attention in the teaching of pronouns, are also interesting. The number of pronouns in our language, as is known, is not limited. Because each part of speech has at least three (more in adverbs) questions, and pronouns used in place of these parts of speech acquire numerous stylistic moments. In the Azerbaijani language, there are wide opportunities for pronouns to be used frequently and in various positions. When teaching interrogative pronouns, some question words, for example, the pronoun "hachan?", should be taken into account. This pronoun is currently used less in our literary language than the interrogative pronoun "ne zaman?". However, until the second half of the 20th century, the interrogative pronoun "hachan?" was more active. Since this pronoun is a literary linguistic fact and occupies a certain place in the texts in textbooks, it cannot be left out of teaching.

In the process of teaching pronouns, one should not forget about the types of structures. The importance of this issue is, on the one hand, the lack of a clear idea about the structure of the pronoun. According to the greatest scholar of Azerbaijani morphology, Mukhtar

Huseynzade, the pronoun has two types of structure (10, 123):

1. Simple pronouns
2. Compound pronouns

Thus, experience and research on the teaching process show that when teaching pronouns, it is necessary to pay attention to the following issues:

1. It is necessary to refer to materials related to pronouns in "Azerbaijani language" textbooks and confirm and reinforce theoretical information with specific language facts. Because if any idea about the language is not proven, it loses its scientific significance. In this regard, it is important to confirm theoretical linguistic ideas with actual materials.

2. When teaching grammatical topics, especially pronouns, attention should be paid to the extent to which they are used in the language. Because pronouns are interesting and rich lexical-grammatical units that confirm the national essence of the Azerbaijani language. In addition, pronouns are among the most frequently used words in our language.

3. During teaching, the issue of which part of speech pronouns are used should not be ignored. In this sense, pronouns should be divided into different groups and taught.

4. When teaching pronouns of the Azerbaijani language, dialect facts related to the topic should also be taken into account.

Experience shows that taking the above into account when teaching pronouns has a positive impact on the quality of the lesson and the ability of learners to absorb information.

It is also necessary to be careful when teaching the pronoun "some". Because this pronoun is a somewhat controversial pronoun. Although it is given among indefinite pronouns in a number of linguistic literatures, these ideas cannot be considered logically correct. In all secondary and higher school grammars, it is indicated that indefinite pronouns are used instead of nouns. Since the pronoun "some" does not have such a position, it cannot be attributed to indefinite pronouns; if it is considered an indefinite pronoun, then the definition given to these pronouns should be changed. In fact, the pronoun "some" has an explanatory feature. From this point of view, it should be included in definite pronouns. However, it should not be forgotten that an indefinite pronoun is also formed on the basis of this pronoun. This happens when it accepts plural and possessive suffixes. It is necessary to take into account the difference in meaning between these words. Thus, the pronoun "some" usually has a determinative feature, and when it accepts plural and possessive suffixes, it has an indefinite feature.

During teaching, one can also encounter confusing moments related to verbs. This especially applies to the infinitive form of the verb. In the Azerbaijani language, there are words with the same composition that are used as both nouns and infinitives. Therefore, they are sometimes confused with nouns.

The confusion of the infinitive with the noun is due to the fact that both of them denote the name. The infinitive denotes the name of the action, and the noun

denotes the name of concrete entities and abstract concepts. Therefore, according to its grammatical meaning, naming is a property that belongs not only to nouns, but also to the infinitive. In fact, the infinitive is a "timeless verb".

Due to its naming property (the name of the action), the infinitive has a common property with the noun and, although it is formed from the verb, it answers the questions of the noun. Therefore, the infinitive cannot bear all the properties of the verb and the noun. It cannot bear the properties of the time category, which is the most basic and important category of the verb, that is, in this respect it is far from the verb. The infinitive cannot take all personal suffixes like a noun (the infinitive only takes the third person ending), does not take plural endings, and cannot be used as a determiner in a sentence.

In this regard, teaching the infinitive requires special attention. Proper linguistic analysis of words that are used as both nouns and infinitives can eliminate the difficulty.

In teaching the Azerbaijani language, practical language materials should be monitored more, their problematic aspects should be revealed. In this sense, the issues of teaching parts of speech attract attention. Although the concepts of parts of speech, and morphological concepts in general, have been studied and analyzed to some extent in Azerbaijani linguistics, it is necessary to conduct a number of studies related to that area of grammar. Thus, researchers who discuss grammar have mainly focused on theoretical issues, while practical work can identify problems more quickly. "Most of the difficulties in the teaching process are related to problems in textbooks. The content of textbooks written long ago sometimes does not meet the requirements of the modern era, and it is sometimes difficult to find sufficient material in them to solve problematic issues. Therefore, there is a need to rework the morphology of the Azerbaijani language by preserving the valuable scientific-theoretical ideas of the past and adding innovations based on factual materials related to the development of science" (Hasanova (2017). p. 16)

CONCLUSION

Experience and research show that in any science, problematic issues arise more often in the teaching process. As in various fields of Azerbaijani linguistics, there are a number of problematic issues in the morphology section, which complicate the teaching of the subject during teaching. Therefore, problems should be taken into account in the explanation of any topic related to the subject and solved in the teaching process. In language issues, the idea of "it's like this in the book" is not the main thing, only the language facts themselves are the main thing. Different linguists can approach these facts from different perspectives and put forward correct and interesting ideas. These ideas generally play a big role in theory. However, language facts are more interesting and convincing not only with their external signs, but also with their levels and shades of meaning. Sometimes a word enters a group as a part of speech, that is, it carries the characteristics of a certain part of speech and is called by its own name. However, when used - within a sentence, different characteristics

arise from that part of speech. This applies more to the adjective-adverb and number-adverb zones.

The Azerbaijani language stands out among the Turkic languages and the world languages in general for its richness and tendency to metaphor, which manifests itself in both theoretical and practical issues. We cannot deny the presence of words in this language that are used as several parts of speech. This is actually one of the qualitative features of the Azerbaijani language. However, such words (in fact, different opinions about words) cause a number of confusions in the teaching process. Such words can be found both among the main and auxiliary parts of speech. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to them in the teaching process and use more optimal teaching options. In this regard, comparisons are of great importance.

References

1. Abdullayev A. (1998). Actual membership and text. Baku, Khazar University.
2. Baliyev H. (2003). Methodology of teaching the Azerbaijani language in secondary school. Baku, ADPU.
3. Jafarov S. (1962). Theoretical foundations of noun teaching. Baku, Azertedrisneshr.
4. Jafarov S. (1983). Transitional processes in parts of speech. Baku, API.
5. Aliyev H. (2006). Comparative teaching of parts of speech (noun and adjective). Baku, Nurlan.
6. Khalilov B. (2007). Morphology of the Azerbaijani language (I, II v.). Baku, Nurlan.
7. Hasanova S. (2017). The place and role of the Azerbaijan language in the teaching of foreign languages. Materials of the International Scientific Conference on "Actual Problems of Learning and Teaching Foreign Languages". Nakhchivan, NSU, p. 14-17.
8. Huseynzadeh Ch. (2004). Morphological norm in the Azerbaijani language. Baku, Nurlan.
9. Guliyeva R., Hajiyev T. (2006). Bibliographic information. Baku, Adiloglu.
10. Mirzazade H. (1990). Historical grammar of the Azerbaijani language. Baku, Azerbaijan University.
11. Nabiyeva Sh. (2010). Actual problems of the methodology of teaching the mother tongue (Methodological manual). Baku, ADPU.
12. Seyidov Y. (2000). Grammar of the Azerbaijani language (morphology). Baku, BSU.